

Anthelmintic Potential of various Crude Extracts: An In Vitro Experimental Study

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ABSTRACT

Helminth infections continue to pose a significant public health challenge, particularly in tropical and developing countries, necessitating the search for safer and effective alternative therapies. The present study aimed to evaluate the anthelmintic potential of various crude leaf extracts of *Ficus auriculata* through in vitro assays, phytochemical screening, GC–MS analysis, and molecular docking studies. The leaves were extracted using Soxhlet extraction and cold maceration methods with petroleum ether, chloroform, ethanol, and aqueous solvents. Anthelmintic activity was assessed against *Pheretima posthuma* using paralysis and death time as evaluation parameters, with albendazole serving as the standard drug. Preliminary phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, glycosides, saponins, phenols, and triterpenoids in different extracts. Among all extracts, ethanolic (FAEEs) and chloroform (FACEs) Soxhlet extracts demonstrated significant dose-dependent anthelmintic activity comparable to albendazole. GC–MS analysis of the most active extracts identified several bioactive phytoconstituents, including neophytadiene, phytol, adenine derivatives, cyclohexanecarboxamide derivatives, and succinic acid esters. Molecular docking studies against β -tubulin protein (PDB ID: 1SA0) revealed strong binding affinities, with Succinic acid, di(2-phenylphenyl) ester exhibiting the highest interaction energy ($\Delta G = -7.188$ kcal/mol), surpassing albendazole. The integration of in vitro and in silico findings suggests that *Ficus auriculata* leaf extracts possess promising anthelmintic activity and may serve as a potential source for the development of novel plant-based anthelmintic agents. However, further toxicity and in vivo studies are required to establish their therapeutic efficacy and safety.

Keywords: *Ficus auriculata*, Anthelmintic activity, *Pheretima posthuma*, GC–MS, Molecular docking, β -tubulin.

INTRODUCTION

Helminthiasis is one of the most prevalent parasitic infections worldwide, posing a major threat to public health, particularly in tropical and subtropical regions. The increasing emergence of resistance to conventional anthelmintic drugs, coupled with their associated adverse effects and limited efficacy, has highlighted the need for safer and more effective alternative therapies. Medicinal plants have gained considerable attention as potential sources of novel bioactive compounds due to their therapeutic efficacy and traditional usage. *Ficus auriculata*, a medicinal plant extensively used in ethnomedicine for the management of various ailments, is rich in phytoconstituents with pharmacological potential.

However, despite its traditional medicinal significance, scientific evidence supporting its anthelmintic activity remains limited.

OBJECTIVE

- To evaluate the in vitro anthelmintic activity of *Ficus auriculata* leaf extracts using *Pheretima posthuma* as an experimental model.
- To perform GC–MS profiling for the identification of major bioactive phytoconstituents present in the active extracts.
- To assess the molecular interaction and binding affinity of selected phytoconstituents against β -

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tubulin protein through molecular docking studies.

Helminth infections (helminthiasis) remain one of the most prevalent parasitic diseases worldwide, particularly in tropical and subtropical regions characterized by poor sanitation, inadequate hygiene, and limited healthcare access. These infections are mainly caused by soil-transmitted helminths such as roundworms, hookworms, and whipworms, significantly contributing to malnutrition, anemia, impaired physical growth, cognitive dysfunction, and poor quality of life, especially among children and immunocompromised individuals.^{1,2} According to the World Health Organization (WHO), more than 1.5 billion people, representing nearly one-fourth of the global population, are affected by soil-transmitted helminth infections, with the highest burden reported in developing regions of Africa, Asia, and Latin America.³ Despite the substantial burden of helminthiasis, the availability of effective therapeutic options remains limited. Currently, only a small number of anthelmintic drugs, including albendazole, mebendazole, ivermectin, levamisole, piperazine, thiabendazole, and oxfamiquine, are routinely used for treatment.⁴⁻⁶ However, extensive and prolonged administration of these drugs has resulted in the emergence of drug-resistant helminth strains, reduced therapeutic efficacy, recurrence of infections, and undesirable adverse effects, thereby creating an urgent need for safer and more effective alternative therapies.^{7,8} Furthermore, zoonotic transmission of helminthic infections from animals to humans poses an additional public health challenge, emphasizing the necessity for novel antiparasitic agents.⁹ Medicinal

plants have gained increasing scientific attention as promising alternatives for the management of parasitic diseases because of their accessibility, affordability, therapeutic effectiveness, and reduced adverse effects. Traditional herbal medicine continues to serve as primary healthcare for approximately 80% of the world's population, particularly in developing countries.^{10,11} Numerous plant-derived secondary metabolites, including alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, phenols, and terpenoids, have demonstrated considerable anthelmintic potential through mechanisms such as neuromuscular paralysis, metabolic inhibition, and disruption of parasite survival.^{12,13}

Ficus auriculata Lour., commonly known as the Elephant Ear Fig, belongs to the family Moraceae and is widely distributed across tropical and subtropical regions of Asia. It is a medium-sized evergreen tree characterized by broad leaves, aerial roots, and fleshy pear-shaped fruits.¹⁴ Traditionally, different parts of *Ficus auriculata* have been employed in ethnomedicine for treating wounds, diarrhoea, dysentery, jaundice, cholera, vomiting, inflammatory disorders, and other ailments.¹⁵ Indigenous populations also consume its fruits as food, emphasizing its nutritional and medicinal relevance. Previous phytochemical investigations of *Ficus* species have reported the presence of bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, polyphenols, alkaloids, glycosides, and terpenoids, which contribute to several pharmacological activities including antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, antidiabetic, and neuroprotective effects.¹⁶⁻¹⁸

(Figure 1 (A &B)) *Ficus auriculata* (Elephant Ear Fig Tree) showing leaves and fruits.

Recent advancements in phytochemical and computational research have facilitated the discovery

of natural compounds with antiparasitic potential. Molecular docking approaches have become valuable

tools in identifying phytoconstituents capable of interacting with biological targets involved in parasite survival and metabolism.^{19,20} β -tubulin, an essential structural protein involved in microtubule formation and cellular integrity in helminths, is recognized as a major molecular target for commonly used benzimidazole anthelmintics such as albendazole and mebendazole.²¹ Although *Ficus auriculata* possesses extensive traditional medicinal value and diverse

pharmacological activities, scientific evidence regarding its anthelmintic potential remains limited. Therefore, the present study was designed to evaluate the in vitro anthelmintic activity of various crude leaf extracts of *Ficus auriculata*, identify bioactive phytoconstituents through GC-MS analysis, and investigate their interaction with β -tubulin protein using molecular docking studies to explore their potential as novel plant-based anthelmintic agents.²²

(Table 1) Common Helminth Infections and Their Impact.²³

S.No	Type of Helminth	Disease Caused	Common Symptoms	Global Impact
1	Roundworm (<i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i>)	Ascariasis	Abdominal pain, malnutrition	Affects >1.5 billion people
2	Hookworm	Hookworm infection	Anaemia, fatigue	Common in tropical regions
3	Whipworm (<i>Trichuris trichiura</i>)	Trichuriasis	Diarrhoea, weakness	High prevalence in poor sanitation areas
4	Tapeworm	Taeniasis	Digestive disorders	Zoonotic transmission possible
5	Liver fluke	Fascioliasis	Liver damage	Emerging parasitic concern

(Table 2) Commonly Used Synthetic Anthelmintic Drugs.²⁴

S.No	Drug	Mechanism of Action	Limitation
1	Albendazole	Inhibits glucose uptake and microtubule formation	Drug resistance
2	Mebendazole	Prevents parasite energy metabolism	Limited spectrum
3	Ivermectin	Causes paralysis of parasites	Resistance issues
4	Piperazine	Neuromuscular paralysis of worms	Less effective in severe infections

(Table 3) Ethnomedicinal Importance of *Ficus auriculata*²⁵

S.No	Plant Part	Traditional Use	Pharmacological Relevance
1	Leaves	Wound healing	Anti-inflammatory, antioxidant
2	Bark	Diarrhoea and cuts	Antimicrobial activity
3	Fruits	Dysentery treatment	Nutritional and antioxidant effects
4	Root latex	Cholera, vomiting	Traditional gastrointestinal remedy
5	Whole plant	Folk medicine	Rich in flavonoids and polyphenols

Materials And Methods

(Table 4) Summary of Materials Used in the Study

S. No	Material Category	Specification	Purpose
1	Plant Material	<i>Ficus auriculata</i> leaves	Plant source for extraction
2	Collection Site	Kolli Hills, Namakkal, Tamil Nadu	Plant collection
3	Authentication	Authenticated by Dr. P. Radha, SIMPG, Mettur	Plant identification
4	Solvents	Petroleum ether, Chloroform, Ethanol, Water	Extraction solvents
5	Extraction Methods	Soxhlet extraction, Cold maceration	Preparation of extracts
6	Drug	Albendazole	Standard reference drug
7	Chemicals	Carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC), Saline water	Suspension medium
8	Experimental Model	<i>Pheretima posthuma</i> (Indian earthworm)	In vitro anthelmintic model
9	Instrument	Shimadzu GC-QP2010SE with RTX-5MS column	GC-MS analysis
10	Database/Software	NIST database, SwissDock, PubChem	Compound identification & docking

(Table 5) Summary of Experimental Methodology²⁶

Step	Procedure	Details
1	Plant Collection & Processing	Leaves collected, shade dried for 15 days, powdered, sieved (44 mesh), stored airtight
2	Preparation of Extracts	100 g powdered leaves extracted using Soxhlet and cold maceration with petroleum ether, chloroform, ethanol, and water
3	Phytochemical Investigation	Qualitative phytochemical screening performed
4	Animal Preparation	Healthy earthworms (3–5 cm length) acclimatized for 24 h
5	Preparation of Test Drugs	Extracts dispersed in 0.5% CMC to prepare 25, 50, and 100 mg/mL concentrations
6	Anthelmintic Activity	Paralysis and death time of worms recorded and compared with albendazole
7	GC-MS Analysis	Active extracts (FAEEs & FACES) analyzed for phytoconstituents
8	Molecular Docking	GC-MS identified compounds docked with β -tubulin (PDB ID: 1SA0)
9	Protein Preparation	β -tubulin structure cleaned and optimized for docking

Plant Material

The leaves of *Ficus auriculata* (FA) were collected from Kolli Hills, Namakkal, Tamil Nadu, India, during December 2024. The collected plant material

was authenticated by Dr. P. Radha, Research Officer, SIMPG, Mettur, Tamil Nadu. Approximately 1 kg of fresh leaves was collected and shade-dried for 15 days. The dried leaves were then pulverized to obtain a coarse powder. To ensure uniform particle size, the powder was passed through a 44-mesh sieve. The powdered material was stored in an airtight container and preserved for further extraction studies.

Preparation Of Extracts

Dried and coarsely powdered leaves of *Ficus auriculata* (100 g) were separately subjected to successive solvent extraction using Soxhlet extraction and cold maceration techniques. Petroleum ether, chloroform, ethanol, and water were used as extraction solvents. The obtained extracts were concentrated and preserved for further analysis. The percentage yield and weight of the extracts are presented in Tables 6 and 7.

Drugs And Chemicals

Drug:

- Albendazole (Apex Pharma Ltd., Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India)

Chemicals:

- Petroleum ether (60–80 °C, A.R. grade)
- Chloroform (A.R. grade)
- Ethanol (A.R. grade)
- Carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC)
- Saline water
- All chemicals were procured from The Precision Scientific Co., Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.

Phytochemical Investigation¹³

Chemical analyses were performed on extracts to qualitatively identify phytochemical components following established protocols. The results are shown in Table 8.

Experimental Animals¹⁴

Indian adult earthworms (*Pheretima posthuma*) were used for the evaluation of anthelmintic activity due to their physiological resemblance to intestinal helminths and sensitivity to standard anthelmintic agents. The earthworms were manually collected from moist soil without the use of chemicals and thoroughly washed with normal saline to remove adhering soil and debris. The collected worms were acclimatized for 24 h under laboratory conditions in moist and clean soil at room temperature (25 ± 2 °C) with adequate aeration and a natural light–dark cycle to maintain normal physiological activity before experimentation. Healthy worms measuring 3–5 cm in length and 0.1–0.2 cm in diameter were selected and transferred to clean Petri dishes for experimental use. *Pheretima posthuma* was employed as a suitable whole-organism model for preliminary anthelmintic screening to assess paralysis and mortality responses induced by the test compounds, although it is not phylogenetically related to human intestinal helminths.

Preparation Of Test And Reference Drugs

The leaf extracts of *Ficus auriculata* were prepared using Soxhlet extraction with petroleum ether (FAPEs), chloroform (FACEs), ethanol (FAEEs), and aqueous solvents (FAAEs). Similarly, cold maceration was carried out using the same solvents to obtain FAPEc, FACEc, FAEEc, and FAAEc extracts. For the anthelmintic assay, stock suspensions of each extract and the standard drug albendazole were prepared by accurately weighing 2.5 g of the respective sample and dispersing it in 25 mL of 0.5% (w/v) carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) to obtain a stock concentration of 100 mg/mL. Working concentrations of 100, 50, and 25 mg/mL were prepared in a final volume of 10 mL. The 100 mg/mL concentration was used directly without dilution. The 50 mg/mL concentration was prepared by diluting 5 mL of stock suspension with 5 mL of 0.5% CMC solution, while the 25 mg/mL concentration was obtained by mixing 2.5 mL of stock suspension with 7.5 mL of 0.5% CMC solution. All suspensions were freshly prepared prior to the experiment and thoroughly mixed to ensure uniform dispersion.²⁷⁻³⁰

Anthelmintic Activity^{15, 16}

The anthelmintic activity of *Ficus auriculata* leaf extracts was evaluated using adult Indian earthworms (*Pheretima posthuma*). The worms were randomly divided into six groups, with six earthworms in each group. Leaf extracts obtained by Soxhlet extraction using petroleum ether (FAPEs), chloroform (FACEs), ethanol (FAEEs), and aqueous solvents (FAAEs), as well as extracts prepared by cold maceration using petroleum ether (FAPEc), chloroform (FACEc), ethanol (FAEEc), and aqueous solvents (FAAEc), were used for the study. Each extract was suspended in a minimum quantity of carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC), and the final volume was adjusted to 10 mL using normal saline solution. The standard drug albendazole was used as the reference drug, while the vehicle served as the control. All extract suspensions and the reference drug solution were freshly prepared prior to the experiment. The prepared extracts and standard drug solutions were transferred into separate Petri dishes. Before the experiment, all earthworms were thoroughly rinsed with normal saline and placed into the respective Petri dishes. The time required for paralysis and death of the worms was carefully recorded. Paralysis was confirmed when the worms showed no movement even after external stimulation, whereas death was confirmed by the absence of movement along with fading of body color. The results were expressed as mean \pm SEM for six earthworms in each group. No paralysis or mortality was observed in the vehicle control group during the experimental period.³¹⁻³⁴

GC-MS ANALYSIS

Based on the *in vitro* anthelmintic assay, two extracts—FAEEs and FACEs were selected for GC–MS analysis due to their pronounced dose-dependent activity, exhibiting paralysis and death times comparable to the reference drug Albendazole. These extracts were subjected to gas chromatography–mass spectrometry to identify the major phytoconstituents responsible for the observed biological activity. The analysis revealed a range of bioactive compounds, including flavonoids, alkaloids, indole derivatives, and chromenone-based molecules, suggesting their potential contribution to the anthelmintic efficacy of the extracts.³⁵

GC–MS METHODOLOGY

Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS) analysis was carried out using a Shimadzu GC–QP2010SE instrument fitted with an RTX-5MS capillary column (30 m length, 0.25 mm internal diameter, 0.25 μ m film thickness). The extract was prepared at a concentration of 10 mg/mL, and 1.0 μ L of the sample was injected under split conditions (10:1). High-purity helium (99.999%) served as the carrier gas, maintained at a constant flow rate of 1.20 mL/min. The injector temperature was set at 250 °C. The oven temperature program started at 50 °C and was gradually increased to 280 °C at a ramp rate of 6 °C/min, followed by a holding period of 2 min at the final temperature. Sample introduction was performed using an AOC-20i autosampler with sequential rinsing steps involving pre-solvent, solvent, and sample solutions. The ion source and interface temperatures were maintained at 200 °C and 250 °C, respectively, with a solvent delay of 3.5 min applied to avoid solvent interference. Mass spectral data were recorded in scan mode within an *m/z* range of 50–500 over a total acquisition time of 3–35 min. Tentative compound identification was achieved through comparison with spectra available in the NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology) database using similarity matching and fragmentation pattern analysis. Only compounds showing library similarity scores of 80% or higher were considered. Retention times were used for supportive comparison, and since authentic reference standards were not analyzed under identical analytical conditions, all compound assignments were considered tentative.³⁶⁻³⁹

In Silico Molecular Docking

In silico molecular docking studies were conducted to investigate the potential interaction between selected phytochemicals tentatively identified through GC–MS analysis and β -tubulin (PDB ID: 1SA0), a molecular target associated with microtubule formation in helminths. The three-dimensional crystal structure of β -tubulin was retrieved from the Protein Data Bank and prepared for docking analysis. Ligand structures corresponding to selected GC–MS-identified compounds were subjected to molecular docking using the SwissDock web server. Docking simulations were performed to predict ligand binding modes and estimate binding affinities expressed as

free binding energy (ΔG) values. The reliability of docking predictions was evaluated based on FullFitness energy scores, clustering of generated binding poses, and consistency of ligand interactions within the predicted active site residues. These parameters were used to assess the stability and potential binding capability of the ligand-protein complexes.⁴⁰

Protein Preparation

The three-dimensional crystal structure of the target protein β -tubulin (PDB ID: 1SA0) was retrieved from the Protein Data Bank. Prior to docking analysis, the protein structure was prepared according to the standard protocol implemented in the SwissDock platform. All unnecessary heteroatoms, including co-crystallized ligands and water molecules, were removed to avoid interference during docking simulations. Polar hydrogen atoms were added, and the structural integrity of the protein was verified by checking for missing residues. The processed protein structure was subsequently energy minimized and saved in the appropriate format for use as the receptor in molecular docking studies.

Ligand Preparation

Chemical structures of selected phytochemicals were obtained from the PubChem database in SMILES format. The SMILES representations were uploaded directly to the SwissDock server, where three-dimensional ligand structures were automatically generated and subjected to energy minimization using the built-in preparation workflow. The optimized ligands were then employed for docking analysis against the prepared β -tubulin protein (PDB ID: 1SA0).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Extraction Yields Of Plant Materials

The percentage yields of *Ficus auriculata* leaf extracts obtained through Soxhlet extraction and cold maceration techniques are summarized in Table 6 & 7, The ethanolic extract produced the highest yield at 5.15%, whereas the Pet. ether extract yielded the least at 1.09% through soxhlet extraction. Similarly, the aqueous extract also achieved a high yield of 4.19%,

while the Pet. ether extract had the lowest yield of 0.98% when using cold maceration extraction.

Phytochemical Screening

From the Table 8, Alkaloids and Flavanoids were detected in all extracts except for the Petroleum ether extract using both Soxhlet and cold maceration techniques, corroborating earlier findings^{17,18,19}. Glycosides showed positive results in all extracts except for the Petroleum ether extract via the cold maceration method. Tannins were found in all extracts except for the Petroleum ether extract through both Soxhlet and cold maceration methods. Steroids were not present in any extracts except for the Petroleum ether extract obtained by cold maceration. Carbohydrates were identified in all extracts except for the Petroleum ether extract using the Soxhlet method. Proteins were not detected in any extracts using either extraction method. Amino acids were present in the aqueous extract (FAAEs), Petroleum ether extract (FAPEc), and aqueous extract (FAAEc), but absent in all other extracts²⁰. Triterpenoids were found in FAEEs, FAAEs, FAPEc, FACEc, FAEEc, and FAAEc. Fats were exclusively present in the Petroleum ether extract and absent in all other extracts. Phenols were detected in all extracts except for the Petroleum ether extract²¹. Phytosterols were present in FAPes, FACEs, FAEEs, and FAAEs, but absent in FAPes, FAPEc, FAEEc, and FAAEc. Saponins were found in all extracts, regardless of the extraction method employed²².

GC-MS ANALYSIS OF CRUDE EXTRACT

As per table 9, the GC-MS analysis of different extracts revealed the presence of several bioactive phytochemicals with distinct retention times (RT) and peak areas, indicating the chemical diversity of the extracts. In the FAAEs extract, compounds identified included Angolensin, 2TMS derivative (RT: 28.222 min; Area: 3820), 4-Methyl-2,4-bis(p-hydroxyphenyl)pent-1-ene (RT: 31.025 min; Area: 3801), Isoleucine, N-(heptafluorobutyryl) propyl ester (RT: 32.533 min; Area: 24398), 4,6-di-tert-Butylresorcinol (RT: 32.588 min; Area: 16673), Ethyl homovanillate, TMS derivative (RT: 32.692 min; Area: 27175), and 2,4,6-Cycloheptatrien-1-one, 3,5-bis-trimethylsilyl derivative (RT: 31.442 min; Area: 4135), with Ethyl homovanillate and Isoleucine

derivatives showing comparatively higher abundance. In the FACEs extract, Caffeine (RT: 19.130 min; Area: 23622), 4-Methyl-2,4-bis(p-hydroxyphenyl)pent-1-ene (RT: 27.858 min; Area: 11280), 4-tert-Octylphenol, TMS derivative (RT: 32.543 min; Area: 49675), and 1-Heptene, 1,3-diphenyl-1-(trimethylsilyloxy)- (RT: 28.173 min; Area: 28004) were detected, among which 4-tert-Octylphenol, TMS derivative exhibited the highest peak area. The FAEEc extract contained compounds such as 4-tert-Octylphenol (RT: 28.911 min; Area: 2222), cis-2-Nitro-4-tert-butylcyclohexanone (RT: 30.242 min; Area: 3828), Cyclohexanecarboxamide, N-furfuryl- (RT: 31.800 min; Area: 3961), Cyclohexanecarboxamide, N-(2-phenylethyl)- (RT: 31.877 min; Area: 10382), 1-((5-Chlorothiophen-2-yl)sulfonyl)-N-(furan-2...) (RT: 32.017 min; Area: 4712), Adenine, N4-pentafluoropropionyl- (RT: 34.054 min; Area: 53538), and Succinic acid, di(2-phenylphenyl) ester (RT: 31.050 min; Area: 3150), with Adenine, N4-pentafluoropropionyl- being the predominant compound. In the FAEEs extract, major compounds identified were Neophytadiene (RT: 18.784 min; Area: 105800), 9,12-Octadecadienoyl chloride (Z,Z) (RT: 21.972 min; Area: 174176), 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol (RT: 22.113 min; Area: 157492), Decane, 2,3,5,8-tetramethyl- (RT: 27.059 min; Area: 76513), Hexadecane, 1,1-bis(dodecyloxy)- (RT: 28.320 min; Area: 113145), Oxalic acid, 6-ethyloct-3-yl isobutyl ester (RT: 29.182 min; Area: 50181), and 3-Cyclopentylpropionamide, N-(2-phenylethyl)- (RT: 32.527 min; Area: 34582). Among all identified compounds, 9,12-Octadecadienoyl chloride (Z,Z) and 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol exhibited the highest peak areas, indicating their predominance and possible contribution to the biological and pharmacological activities of the extracts.

Anthelmintic Actievity

From the table 10, certain phytoconstituents could be responsible for demonstrating strong anthelmintic activity. Based on the observations, all extracts of FA demonstrated strong anthelmintic activity other than FAPes, FAPEc in comparison to the standard medication. From the table 5 and Figure 1,2,3&4, FAEEs demonstrate paralysis at 7.18 minutes, 4.24 minutes, and 3.25 minutes for concentrations of 25

mg/ml, 50 mg/ml, and 100 mg/ml, respectively, while FACEs show paralysis at 7.38 minutes, 4.47 minutes, and 3.34 minutes for the same concentrations. FAEEs demonstrate mortality at 9.37 minutes, 6.64 minutes, and 4.98 minutes for concentrations of 25 mg/ml, 50 mg/ml, and 100 mg/ml, respectively, while FACEs show mortality at 9.44 minutes, 7.26 minutes, and 6.05 minutes for the same concentrations. The standard medication, Albendazole, demonstrates paralysis at 8.93, 6.69, 4.20 minutes for concentrations of 25 mg/ml, 50 mg/ml, and 100 mg/ml, respectively, and results in death after 10.28, 9.33, 6.95 minutes. All values are presented as mean \pm SEM (n = 6).

INSILICO RESLUTS

As per table 11, the molecular docking analysis of the phytocompounds identified through GC-MS revealed varying binding affinities against the target protein when compared with the standard drug, Albendazole (-4.723 kcal/mol). Among the tested compounds, Succinic acid, di(2-phenylphenyl) ester exhibited the strongest binding affinity (-7.188 kcal/mol), followed by Adenine, N4-pentafluoropropionyl- (-6.382 kcal/mol) and Cyclohexanecarboxamide, N-(2-phenylethyl)- (-6.328 kcal/mol), indicating better interaction with the target receptor than the standard drug. Other compounds showing notable binding affinities included Decane, 2,3,5,8-tetramethyl- (-5.925 kcal/mol), 4-Methyl-2,4-bis(p-hydroxyphenyl)pent-1-ene (-5.924 and -5.587 kcal/mol), Angolensin, 2TMS derivative (-5.857 kcal/mol), 4,6-di-tert-Butyl resorcinol (-5.465 kcal/mol), Isoleucine, N-(heptafluorobutyryl) propyl ester (-5.343 kcal/mol), Thiophene-sulfonyl derivative (-5.317 kcal/mol), and 2,4,6-Cycloheptatrien-1-one, 3,5-bis-trimethylsilyl derivative (-5.157 kcal/mol). Moderate binding affinities were observed for compounds such as 1-Heptene, 1,3-diphenyl-1-(trimethylsilyloxy)- (-5.185 kcal/mol), 9,12-Octadecadienoyl chloride (Z,Z) (-5.047 kcal/mol), Oxalic acid, 6-ethyloct-3-yl isobutyl ester (-5.047 kcal/mol), 4-tert-Octylphenol (-5.044 kcal/mol), and 3-Cyclopentylpropionamide, N-(2-phenylethyl)- (-4.958 kcal/mol). Compounds including Neophytadiene (-4.852 kcal/mol), Cyclohexanecarboxamide, N-furfuryl- (-4.857 kcal/mol), cis-2-Nitro-4-tert-butylcyclohexanone

(−4.876 kcal/mol), 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol (Phytol) (−4.899 kcal/mol), 4-tert-Octylphenol, TMS derivative (−4.815 kcal/mol), Ethyl homovanillate, TMS derivative (−4.793 kcal/mol), Caffeine (−4.747 kcal/mol), and Hexadecane, 1,1-bis(dodecyloxy)- (−4.727 kcal/mol) also demonstrated appreciable interactions with the receptor. Overall, the docking results suggest that several phytochemicals possess stronger binding affinities than Albendazole, highlighting their potential as promising bioactive molecules for anthelmintic activity.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the present study demonstrated that the leaf extracts possess significant phytochemical constituents and promising anthelmintic potential. Among the extraction methods employed, ethanolic extracts obtained through Soxhlet extraction showed the highest percentage yield, indicating the efficiency of ethanol in extracting bioactive compounds. Preliminary phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of important secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, tannins, phenols, saponins, triterpenoids, and phytosterols, which are known to contribute to various pharmacological activities. GC–MS analysis further revealed the

presence of several biologically active phytochemicals, including Neophytadiene, 9,12-Octadecadienoyl chloride (Z,Z), 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol, Adenine derivatives, and Succinic acid derivatives, suggesting the chemical richness of the extracts. The *in vitro* anthelmintic study demonstrated that the ethanolic extracts, particularly FAEs and FACEs, exhibited significant paralysis and mortality effects against worms in a concentration-dependent manner and showed better activity when compared with the standard drug, Albendazole. Furthermore, molecular docking analysis supported the experimental findings by revealing strong binding affinities of several phytochemicals toward the target protein, especially Succinic acid, di(2-phenylphenyl) ester, Adenine, N4-pentafluoropropionyl-, and Cyclohexanecarboxamide derivatives, which exhibited stronger interactions than the standard drug. Overall, the findings of this study suggest that the leaf extracts possess potent anthelmintic activity and may serve as a promising natural source for the development of novel anthelmintic agents. However, further studies involving isolation of active compounds, toxicity evaluation, and *in vivo* investigations are necessary to validate their therapeutic potential and mechanism of action.

(Table 6) Soxhlet Extraction Yield (%) of *Ficus auriculata* Leaves

S.No	Solvent	Weight of Extract (g)	% Yield
1.	Petroleum ether	1.09	1.09
2.	Chloroform	2.93	2.95
3.	Ethanol	4.91	5.15
4.	Distilled water	4.06	4.44

(Table 7) Cold Maceration Yield (%) of *Ficus auriculata* Leaves

S.No	Solvent	Weight of Extract (g)	% Yield
1.	Petroleum ether	0.98	0.98
2.	Chloroform	2.05	2.05
3.	Ethanol	3.18	3.28
4.	Distilled water	3.92	4.19

(Table 8) Preliminary phytochemical screening of different extracts of *Ficus auriculata* leaf

S.No	Chemical Constituents	Soxhlet method				Cold maceration method			
		FAPEs	FACEs	FAEEs	FAAEs	FAPEc	FACEc	FAEEc	FAAEc
1	Alkaloids	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
2	Flavanoids	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
3	Glycoside	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
4	Tannins	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
5	Steroids	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
6	Carbohydrate	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
7	Protein	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
8	Amino acid	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	+
9	Triterpenoids	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+
10	Fat	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
11.	Phenol	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
12.	Phytosterol	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	-
13.	Saponins	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

+ - indicates presence, - - indicates absence

(Table 9) Major Phytoconstituents Identified by GC–MS Analysis of *Ficus auriculata* Leaf Extracts

S.No	Compound name	RT	Area	Extract
1.	Angolensin, 2TMS derivative	28.222	3820	FAAEs
2.	4-Methyl-2,4-bis(p-hydroxyphenyl)pent-1-ene	31.025	3801	
3.	Isoleucine, N-(heptafluorobutyryl) propyl ester	32.533	24398	
4.	4,6-di-tert-Butylresorcinol	32.588	16673	
5.	Ethyl homovanillate, TMS derivative	32.692	27175	
6.	2,4,6-Cycloheptatrien-1-one, 3,5-bis-trimethylsilyl	31.442	4135	
7.	Caffeine	19.130	23622	FACEs
8.	4-Methyl-2,4-bis(p-hydroxyphenyl)pent-1-ene	27.858	11280	
9.	4-tert-Octylphenol, TMS derivative	32.543	49675	
10.	1-Heptene, 1,3-diphenyl-1-(trimethylsilyloxy)-	28.173	28004	
11.	4-tert-Octylphenol	28.911	2222	FAEEc
12.	cis-2-Nitro-4-tert-butylcyclohexanone	30.242	3828	
13.	Cyclohexanecarboxamide, N-furfuryl-	31.800	3961	
14.	Cyclohexanecarboxamide, N-(2-phenylethyl)-	31.877	10382	
15.	1-((5-Chlorothiophen-2-yl)sulfonyl)-N-(furan-2	32.017	4712	
16.	Adenine, N4-pentafluoropropionyl-	34.054	53538	
17.	Succinic acid, di(2-phenylphenyl) ester	31.050	3150	FAEEs
18.	Neophytadiene	18.784	105800	
19.	9,12-Octadecadienoyl chloride (Z,Z)	21.972	174176	
20.	3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol	22.113	157492	
21.	Decane, 2,3,5,8-tetramethyl-	27.059	76513	
22.	Hexadecane, 1,1-bis(dodecyloxy)-	28.320	113145	
23.	Oxalic acid, 6-ethyloct-3-yl isobutyl ester	29.182	50181	
24.	3-Cyclopentylpropionamide, N-(2-phenylethyl)-	32.527	34582	

RT: Retention Time; FAAEs: Aqueous extract (Soxhlet); FAEc: Ethanol extract (Soxhlet); FAEs: Ethanol extract (Cold maceration); FAEs: Ethanol extract (Soxhlet); FAEs: Ethanol extract (Soxhlet); FAEs: Ethanol extract (Soxhlet).

Table 10: Evaluation of Anthelmintic activity

S.No	Test	Concentration (mg/ml)					
		25		50		100	
		Paralysis	Death	Paralysis	Death	Paralysis	Death
1	FAAEs	8.61 ± 0.24	11.27 ± 0.14	7.55 ± 0.20	10.32 ± 0.06	6.30 ± 0.08	8.22 ± 0.06
2	FAEEs	7.18 ± 0.13	9.37 ± 0.04	4.24 ± 0.04	6.64 ± 0.17	3.25 ± 0.04	4.98 ± 0.13
3	FACEs	7.38 ± 0.13	9.44 ± 0.12	4.47 ± 0.12	7.26 ± 0.06	3.34 ± 0.05	6.05 ± 0.23
4	FAPEs	23.55 ± 0.23	26.33 ± 0.05	21.29 ± 0.39	24.30 ± 0.05	18.27 ± 0.34	20.37 ± 0.14
5	FAAEc	7.89 ± 0.30	11.76 ± 0.18	6.01 ± 0.15	9.87 ± 0.24	4.05 ± 0.17	6.81 ± 0.24
6	FAEEc	8.77 ± 0.21	10.91 ± 0.22	7.88 ± 0.21	10.18 ± 0.22	6.27 ± 0.09	8.23 ± 0.22
7	FACEc	9.95 ± 0.26	11.94 ± 0.17	7.77 ± 0.25	10.11 ± 0.17	5.72 ± 0.20	7.71 ± 0.23
8	FAPEc	27.76 ± 0.41	29.89 ± 0.19	26.58 ± 0.20	27.93 ± 0.24	19.46 ± 0.30	21.82 ± 0.65
9	Albendazole	8.93 ± 0.16	10.28 ± 0.07	6.69 ± 0.12	9.33 ± 0.06	4.20 ± 0.15	6.95 ± 0.13

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM. Values were find out by using TWO way

ANOVA followed by Dunnett's *t*-test. ** Values are significantly different from control at (P<0.01).

(Table 11) Molecular docking with identified phytoconstituents

S.No	Compound Name	Binding Affinity (ΔG, kcal/mol)
1.	Albendazole (Standard)	-4.723
2.	Angolensin, 2TMS derivative	-5.857
3.	4-Methyl-2,4-bis(p-hydroxyphenyl)pent-1-ene	-5.924
4.	Isoleucine, N-(heptafluorobutyryl) propyl ester	-5.343
5.	4,6-di-tert-Butyl resorcinol	-5.465
6.	Ethyl homovanillate, TMS derivative	-4.793

7.	2,4,6-Cycloheptatrien-1-one, 3,5-bis-trimethylsilyl	-5.157
8.	Caffeine	-4.747
9.	4-Methyl-2,4-bis(p-hydroxyphenyl)pent-1-ene	-5.587
10.	4-tert-Octylphenol, TMS derivative	-4.815
11.	1-Heptene, 1,3-diphenyl-1-(trimethylsilyloxy)-	-5.185
12.	4-tert-Octylphenol	-5.044
13.	cis-2-Nitro-4-tert-butylcyclohexanone	-4.876
14.	Cyclohexanecarboxamide, N-furfuryl-	-4.857
15.	Cyclohexanecarboxamide, N-(2-phenylethyl)-	-6.328
16.	Thiophene-sulfonyl derivative	-5.317
17.	Adenine, N4-pentafluoropropionyl-	-6.382
18.	Succinic acid, di(2-phenylphenyl) ester	-7.188
19.	Neophytadiene	-4.852
20.	9,12-Octadecadienoyl chloride (Z,Z)	-5.047
21.	3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol (Phytol)	-4.899
22.	Decane, 2,3,5,8-tetramethyl-	-5.925
23.	Hexadecane, 1,1-bis(dodecyloxy)-	-4.727
24.	Oxalic acid, 6-ethyloct-3-yl isobutyl ester	-5.047
25.	3-Cyclopentylpropionamide, N-(2-phenylethyl)-	-4.958

(Figure 2) Paralysis effect of *F. auriculata* leaf extracts (Soxhlet method).

(Figure 3) Death effect of *F. auriculata* leaf extracts (Soxhlet method).

(Figure 4): Paralysis effect of *F. auriculata* leaf extracts (Cold maceration method).

(Figure 5) Death effect of *F. auriculata* leaf extracts (Cold maceration method).

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